

Lipid degrading enzymes as drug alternative against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*

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Mycobacterium tuberculosis, a causative agent of tuberculosis, is one of the most flourishing pathogen human has ever come across. This is due to its ability to fight with the immune system of the host, restraining the complete host defence system to carry on in the host cells. Till date, majority of the drugs target upon the budding bacterium and not the quiescent ones.

During hypoxic conditions or dormancy, the mycobacterium derives energy from the stored lipids and consumes them as carbon source to stay alive. Not only the lipases, but lipolytic enzymes, such as phospholipase C, induce macrophage membrane lysis in *M. tuberculosis*. In other pathogen, which infects human beings, the secretory lipid degrading enzymes help in hydrolysis of cell membrane of host to adhere with the host cell. Genome sequence analysis of the *M. tuberculosis* has disclosed that it contains 250 enzymes involved in lipid metabolism, as compared to *Escherichia coli* which carries 50 only. Among these enzymes, a family of 21 carboxyl ester hydrolases, called Lip (A to W, except K and S), have been annotated as putative esterases or lipases. Studies are underway to explore all these lipolytic enzymes to develop a novel drug target.

Keywords : *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, lipases, lipid degrading enzymes.

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